

ASSESSMENT OF THE LEVEL OF INVOLVEMENT OF PARENT AND TEACHERS' IN RUNNING ALMAJIRI INTEGRATED SCHOOL PROGRAM IN SABON-BIRNI LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, SOKOTO STATE, NIGERIA

By

Attahiru Ahmad Sifawa,¹

Lukman Umar Sifawa²

Department of Educational Foundations, Sokoto State University, Sokoto
and

Murtala Marafa³

^{1&3}Department of History, Sokoto State University, Sokoto

Abstract

This study investigates the level of involvement of Parents and Teachers' in running the *Almajiri* Integrated School Program. The research design for the study is descriptive survey. The design is found to be more applicable, appropriate and relevant to the study, because of the assertion of Mahesh, Sara, and Neena (2011) that, descriptive survey design is used in any study that portrays the characteristics of a group or individual, or a situation under study or describing in a systematic manner, the characteristics, features, or facts about a given population. The population of the study comprises all the teaching Staff of the school and parents of pupils enrolled in the school. There were 17 teachers in the school with 323 pupils. The sample size of 17 teachers and 110 parents were randomly selected and was based on Research Advisor (2006) table for determining sample size. The researcher used proportionate and random sampling techniques in order to give equal chance of being selected among the parents. The research instrument is a self-constructed questionnaire which is used as the main instrument for data collection during the study. The instrument is validated by a team of expert in education from the Faculty of Education, Sokoto State University, Sokoto. The reliability of the instrument is found at 0.75. The study reveals that Parents are not directly or indirectly involved in running the affairs of the Program. Therefore, the study recommends that parents should be involved in the affairs of the Program in order to make it more interesting to the students and community.

Key Words: Parent and Teachers' Involvement, *Almajiri* Integrated School Program

Introduction

Islam came to Hausa land around eleventh century as reported by Balogun (Balogun, 1980), and that by 15th to 16th centuries, Kano, Zazzau, Katsina (Yandoto) had become great centers of Islamic learning (Albasu, 1997). After the Sokoto Jihad of nineteenth century, Islamic scholarship further blossomed and spread across the whole of the present northern Nigeria. The Jihad leaders alone bequeathed to us not less than five hundred materials ranging from books, pamphlets, epistles, treatises, etc. in various field of mundane and spiritual matters. According to El-miskin (1997), rulers of Kanem-Bornu supported the Qur'anic schools to the extent that they themselves were involved in Qur'anic literacy. Teachers of Qur'anic schools were given economic and political protection and motivation they needed.

Moreover, according to Khalid (1997), during the classical days of Sokoto and Borno Caliphates. *Mallams* were accorded grants and privileges called *Mahram*. It was a written document given to Qur'anic teachers by the ruler certifying that the bearer, his family and descendants and sometimes his followers were exempted from some state obligations such as military conscription, taxes, and palace duties and so on. The document sometimes specified grants of land allocated to the bearer, his

family and his disciples to cultivate the land and farm free from taxation, confiscation and any form of fief control. Muslim scholars were also included among the beneficiaries of zakat. This was the condition of Islamic scholarship before the advent of colonialism in Northern Nigeria (Shehu, 2005).

However, there has been several efforts to reform Islamic education globally, Nigeria inclusive. These efforts were triggered by the challenges posed to the Muslim Ummah over the government's financial and institutional support to the alien western and secular system of education at the expense of the old Islamic system of education. In Nigeria, this effort started with the Kano seminar in 1976 at Bayero University College, Kano. Other efforts include introduction of Islamiyya school system which was started by a group of youths in Zaria city. After some resistance from some elites in the society that associated that move with political motives, the system gradually attained success and acceptance in many parts of northern Nigeria. By 1970, almost all cities in Northern Nigeria have a fair number of Islamiyya schools.

The most recent move by the government to support Islamic education was the introduction of integration approach which gave rise to the establishment of *Almajiri* Integrated

Schools in many states of the Northern part of the country, Sokoto state inclusive. The Program was launched by the government of former President Goodluck Ebele Jonathan in 2010. The objectives of the Program include among others: to provide access and equal opportunity for Basic Education to all school-age children (*Almajirai*); to discourage and gradually eliminate itinerancy and street begging by *Almajirai* in the country; to facilitate positive integration of Islamic and western Education, etc. The-strategic Framework of the Program include among others; establishment of integrated *Almajiri* Model Schools; transforming the existing *Tsangaya* Schools into Model *Almajiri* Integrated Schools; and to provide support for community owned *Tsangaya*/Islamyyah and *Tahfeez* Primary schools, with a view to upgrading and modernizing them. Some of the achievements of the Program include among others: Development and production of National Framework for the development and integration of *Almajiri* Education and other manuals that specified the intervention strategies across the states of the Federation and the Federal Capital Territory, as well as commencement of academic activities in the completed schools. This study therefore intends to find out whether the Program is running based on the

framework it was established upon or not, and to assess the level of achievements recorded by the Program as well as the challenges facing the proper implementation of the Program and its impact in Sokoto state.

Statement of the Problem/Justification

In Nigeria, the number of out of school children stood at about 9 million by 2010 and a vast majority of these children are *Almajiri* pupils mostly found in Northern part of the country. Several concerted efforts were made with a view to curtailing the menace of street begging engaged by these children in the name of questing for Qur'anic education which makes them vulnerable to untold discrimination, hardship, infectious diseases arising from the lifestyle they adopted, child labour and a host of other inhuman downgrading treatment meted against the *Almajiri* by the society. The National *Almajiri* Integrated Model School Program introduced and launched in Sokoto state by the administration of former President Goodluck Ebele Jonathan in 2010 was believed by many stakeholders to be among the positive steps taken as a viable means of integrating Islamic education with western education, thereby winning the minds of the *Almajiri* pupils, their parents and teachers as well as Muslim community to support and patronize the

Program. Unfortunately, recent studies on the Program revealed a lot of challenges facing the Program in some states where it was established. These challenges include but not limited to: Low level awareness on the existence of the schools (Program) by the supposed beneficiaries (rural Muslim communities); Lack of confidence in the Integration the schools are intended to achieve among the populace; poor implementation and abuse of the Program; poor funding; poor enrolment; shortage of necessary facilities; problem of feeding etc.

Objectives of the Research

The specific objectives of the study are as follows:

- i. To assess the level of involvement of parents of *Almajiri* pupils in the running of the Program;
- ii. To assess the level of involvement of parents of *Almajiri* pupils in the running of the Program;

Research Questions

The study intends to answer the following research questions:

- i. What is the level of involvement of parents of *Almajiri* pupils in the running of the Program;
- ii. What is the level of involvement of Teachers' of *Almajiri* pupils in the running of the Program;

Research Methodology

The research design for the study is descriptive survey. The design is only interested in describing the events as they are (Nvvorgu, 2006). There is one *Almajiri* Integrated School in Sabon Birni Local Government. Population of the study comprises all the teaching Staff of the school and parents of pupils enrolled in the school. There were 17 teachers in the school with 323 pupils. The sample size of 17 teachers and 110 parents were randomly selected and was based on Research Advisor (2006) table for determining sample size. The researcher used proportionate and random sampling techniques in order to give equal chance of being selected among the parents.

Table 1: Population of the Study

S/N	Name of School	No. of teacher	No. of Parents
1	Almajiri Integrated School, Sabon Birni, Sokoto State	17	131
Total		17	131

Source: SUBEB, 2020

The sample size of 110 out of 131 population of parents and 17 teachers was based on Research Advisors (2006) table for determining sample size. The researcher used proportionate and random sampling techniques in order to give equal opportunity of being selected among the parents. The justification for

its use is based on the assertion of Ilker, Sulaiman, and Rukayya (2015) that convenience sampling is used when the selected members meet certain criteria such as easy accessibility, geographical proximity and availability at a given time or the willingness to participate.

A self-constructed questionnaire was used as the main instrument for data collection during the study. The questionnaire contains relevant questions on the variables of the study. Both open ended and close ended questions will be provided for the respondents to freely express their views. Moreover, a structured interview was used as another instrument for data collection in order to checkmate the data collected via the semi structured questionnaire which is the

main instrument for data collection of the study. The data for the study were collected via the semi- structured questionnaire as the main instrument for data collection of the study. More so, data were also collected via the structured interview to checkmate the data collected via the main instrument of data collection as explained earlier. The data collected via the semi- structured questionnaire were analyzed using simple percentage and frequencies to represent the responses of the respondents. While data collected via the structured interview were analyzed quantitatively using content analysis thereby reporting verbatim the responses of the respondents.

Results

Table 2: Involvement of Teachers’ into *Almajiri* Integrated Schools Program

S/N	Item Statement	Options				Percentage	
		G	P	A	D	%	%
1	Do you think <i>Almajiri</i> integrated schools have actually reduced the menace of street begging in our society?			2	8	20%	80%
2	What is your view on the adequacy or otherwise of the number of <i>Almajiri</i> Integrated schools in our society?			1	9	10%	90%
3	What is your assessment on how <i>Almajiri</i> Integrated Schools are run?	G	P	3	7	30%	70%
4	What is your view on the assertion that most of the pupils in the <i>Almajiri</i> integrated schools are not street begging children supposed to be targeted by the Program?			1	9	10%	90%
5	What is your view on the assertion that the Program is politicized especially in terms of school locations and admission?			10	0	100%	0%
6	What is your view on proper implementation of the Program?	G	P	2	8	20%	80%
7	What is your assessment on the level of support the Program is receiving from the members of the public especially parent?	G	P	7	3	70%	30%
8	What is your view on the curriculum content of the Program as far			8	2	80%	20%

	the integration of Islamic and Western Education?				
9	Do you think there is adequate awareness of the public on the existence of the Program?	7	3	70%	30%
10	What is your view on whether the Program should be sustained or discarded and why?	10	0	100%	0%
	Grant Total	51	49	50.1%	49.0%

Source Field Work (2022)

The responses of table 2 above revealed that Teachers were fully involved in the running affairs of Almajiri Integrated School Program in Sabon-Birni Local Government Area. Item one in the table indicated that 80% of the respondents did not agree that Almajiri integrated schools have actually reduced the menace of street begging in our society while 20% of the respondents agreed. Item two of the table shows that 90% of the respondents believed that the number of schools were not enough in our society, while 10% of the respondents believed that they are enough. Item three of the table revealed that 70% of the respondents agreed that *Almajiri* Integrated Schools is poorly run while 30% of the respondents believed that the Program run smoothly. Item four of the table 90% of the respondents agreed that pupils enrolled into *Almajiri* integrated schools are not street begging children while 10% of the respondents did not agree. Item five of the table indicated that 100% of the respondents

agreed that the Program is politicized especially in terms of school locations and admission. Item six of the table shows that 80% of the respondents believed that the Program is poorly implemented while 20% of the respondents said no. Item seven of the table indicated that 70% of the respondents agreed that the Program is receiving support from the members of the public especially parents while 30% did not agree. Item eight of the table shows that 80% of the respondents agreed that the curriculum content of the Program as far the integration of Islamic and Western Education while 20% did not agree. Item nine of the table shows that 70% of the respondents agreed that there is adequate awareness of the public on the existence of the Program while 30% of the respondents did not agree. Item ten of the table indicates that 100% of the respondents agreed that the Program should be sustained and improved.

Table 3: Involvement of Parents' into *Almajiri* Integrated Schools Program

S/N	Item Statement	Options		Percentage	
		Agree	Disagree	%	%
1	Are you aware of the existence of <i>Almajiri</i> Integrated Schools in your area?	10	0	100%	0%
2	Are your children/wards involved into street begging?	6	4	60%	40%
3	In your own view, is street begging or house to house begging a prerequisite for seeking Qur'anic Education?	3	7	30%	70%
4	Do you normally send your children to Qur'anic school away from your locality?	7	3	70%	30%
5	Do you provide food provision and other necessities of life to your children when sending them to Qur'anic schools?	1	9	10%	90%
6	Are you aware of the risk involved in sending children to far places for Qur'anic Education?	6	4	60%	40%
7	Do you agree that it is better and more appropriate for children to learn Qur'anic Education within their various localities where they can easily be monitored by their parents?	6	4	60%	40%
8	Do you consider the interest of your children/wards before sending them to far places for Qur'anic Education?	0	10	0%	100%
9	Don't you think allowing your child to engage in street begging is tantamount to relinquishing your responsibility as a parent(s)?	3	7	30%	70%
10	Are you satisfied with the level of government effort in the area of traditional Qur'anic education?	3	7	30%	70%
11	Do you normally seek the opinion of mothers before sending your children to a far place for traditional Qur'anic education and why?	0	10	0%	100%
Grant Total		42	68	38%	62%

Source Field Work (2022)

The responses of table 3 above revealed that parents are not fully involved in the running affairs of *Almajiri* Integrated School Program in Sabon-Birni Local Government Area. Item one in the table indicated that 100% of the respondents agreed that, they are

aware of the existence of *Almajiri* Integrated Schools in their area. Item two of the table shows that 60% of the respondents agree that, their children/wards involved into street begging, while 40% of the respondents did not agree. Item three of the table

revealed that 30% of the respondents agreed that street begging or house to house begging is a prerequisite for seeking Qur'anic Education while 70% of the respondents did not agree. Item four of the table 70% of the respondents send their children to Qur'anic school away from their locality while 30% of the respondents did not. Item five of the table indicated that, only 10% of the respondents used to provide food provision and other necessities of life to their children while sending them to Qur'anic schools while 90% of the respondents did not. Item six of the table shows that 60% of the respondents are aware of the risk involved in sending children to far places for Qur'anic Education while 40% of the respondents said no. Item seven of the table indicated that 60% of the respondents agree that it is better and more appropriate for children to learn Qur'anic Education within their various localities where they can easily be monitored by their parents while 40% did not agree. Item eight of the table shows that 100% of the respondents do not consider the interest of their children/wards before sending them to far places for Qur'anic Education. Item nine of the table shows that 30% of the respondents think allowing their children to engage in street begging is tantamount to relinquishing their responsibility as parent(s) while

70% of the respondents did not agree. Item ten of the table indicates that 30% of the respondents are satisfied with the level of government effort in the area of traditional Qur'anic education while 70% of the respondents are not. Item 11 of the table shows that 100% of the respondents do not seek the opinion of mothers before sending their children to a far place for traditional Qur'anic education because they are the household's heads.

Summary of the Major Findings

Findings of the study shows that:

- i. Teachers' were fully involved in the running affairs of *Almajiri* Integrated School Program in Sabon-Birni Local Government Area.
- ii. Parents were not fully involved in the running affairs of *Almajiri* Integrated School Program in Sabon-Birni Local Government Area

Discussion of the Findings

The findings of this study revealed that, Teachers' were fully involved in the running affairs of *Almajiri* Integrated School Program in Sabon-Birni Local Government Area, the findings of this study is in line with Mashema, and Kawu, (2017) whose study revealed that, most of the teachers are aware of the integration process and government has made various effort to integrate the two systems in Azare

Tsangaya Model Boarding Primary School. The study also found that the current integration drive should be seen as genuine and purposeful educational endeavor that must not only be supported but should be incorporated within the mainstream of our educational policies. The outcome of the study reveals that, it has been adequately clear that the enrolment drive was poor in the school. However, the findings of this study conquered with the Indabawa, A. S. (2005) underscores the need to design curriculum to reflect the philosophy of Islamic education. He maintains that the foundation of any progressive culture or civilization lies on the central theme of philosophy of its epistemology. For this Program to succeed therefore, proper identification, analysis and interpretation of the precept of Islamic educational philosophy should be done. Such precept according to him should be drawn from the Qur'an, Hadith and legacy of the *Salaf*, particularly from their thought, policies and proposals.

This study also found that, Parents were not fully involved in running the affairs of Almajiri Integrated School Program in Sabon-Birni Local Government Area, this finding conquered with Babagana, Idris, Ndagi, Danjumma, and Abdullahi, (2022) also affirmed that a strategies for improving Almajiri Integrated School Program, the Program

should be fully funded, vocational skills should be introduced into the system, private sector should participate, parents should be charged fees and policy should be enacted. Abubakar and Njoku (2015) found that, most students in *Almajiri* Integrated Model School performed far better in Islamic Studies than their counterparts in the conventional schools in Sokoto Metropolis. However, Bashir, Abdurrahman, & Yawale, (2018) found that parents have abandoned their obligations of properly taking care and educating their children. This maybe the reason why societies neglect the street beggars known as *Almajirai* and sometimes look down on them. It is argued for the parents to look after their children even if they are not together with them.

Conclusion

The Almajiri Integrated School Program was launched by the government of former President Goodluck Ebele Jonathan in 2010. Despite the effort made by his administration and huge resources invested into the Program to ensure that it was successful, a large number of the target children are not be able be enrolled and are still roaming about on the street and do not have access to the formal education.

Recommendations

The study made the following recommendations:

- i. Teachers' should be fully involved in running the affairs of the Program since whatever the plan of the Program, they are the ones to implement it.
- ii. There should be proper sensitization or awareness for the parents and school administrators as well as involving them in the running the affairs of the Program.

References

- Abubakar, B .G. & Njoku, J. N. (2015). *Influence of Almajiri on School Attendance and Academic Performance among students of Amajiri Integrated Model School, Sokoto State*. World Journal of Education, 5 (4), 58-63. <https://doi:10.5430/wje.v5n4p58>
- Babagana, M. Idris, U.S., Ndagi, M., Danjumma, A.M. and Abdullahi, M.K. (2022). *Assessment of Almajiri System of Education: Its Implication for Child's Family and National Development in Minna Metroplis, Niger State, Nigeria*. Available on <https://C:/Users/USER/22.pdf>
- Bashir, L.M., Abdurrrhman, I.I. & Yawale, M. (2018). *The Challenges of Almajiri System of Education To Social Peace In Nigeria: A Cross-Sectional Investigation*
- Dauda, A. (2005). *Educational Integration as a Strategy for Muslim Educational Reforms*.
- Elmiskin, T. (1997). *Islamic Education in Northern Nigeria and the Crisis of Subsistence" A paper For National Conference on Begging and Destitution at Arewa House, Kaduna*.
- Galadanci, S. A. S. (1993). *Islamic Education in Africa: Past Influence and Contemporary Challenges*.
- Ilker, E. Sulaiman, A. M. and Rukayya, S.A (2015). Comparison of convenience sampling and purposive sampling. *American journal of theoretical and applied statistics (5) 1-4*
- Indabawa, A. S. (2005). *Educational Philosophy and Muslim Educational Reform: Some Discussion*.
- Khalid, S. (1997). *Institutional Support for Muslim Educational Reform*
- Mahesh, C, Sara T. and Neenah, T (2011). *Social Research Methods*. University of Calcut School of Distance Education. Published by Calcut University, Malappuram and Kerela, India.
- Mashema, B.M. and Kawu, G. S (2017). *Integration of Traditional Islamic Education with Western Education Schools Model: A case Study of Azarc Tsangaya Model Boarding Primary School*.
- Maxwell, J.A. (1997). *Qualitative Research Design: An interactive Approach*. Sage Journal. George Manson University.

- Sa'ad, G. (2005). Curriculum Development and Muslim Educational Reform.
- Shehu, S. (2005). Muslim Educational Reforms Activities in Nigeria: History, Trends Issues and Future Directions.
- Sirajo, M.S. Mukhtar, S. Usman, A.I. Ubadawaki, U and Sifawa, A.A. (2018). Situation of Almajiri School, Gagi. Sokoto: Its Achievements and Challenges from inception to Date. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Sciences*, Vol. II issue iv.
- Sneidelor, C. (1939). Behavioural Research. A Conceptual Approach. *Sage Journal*
- Sulaiman S. (2005). Funding and Sustainability of Muslim Educational Reforms.